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SECTION 1: INTRODUCTION

The objective of the GTCLC-NEG MSCA-IF project is to evaluate the potential of the pressurized chemical looping combustion (PCLC) to produce electricity with CO₂ capture by integrating the PCLC unit with a gas turbine. In order to achieve high energy efficiency, the PCLC unit should operate at elevated temperature, in the range of 1000-1200 °C. One of the critical issues related to the development of the PCLC process is to be confident on the oxygen carrier performance at such high temperatures.

This work was focused on the evaluation of oxygen carrier materials during their redox cycling at suitable temperatures for the PCLC process. These materials were based on iron and nickel, which were selected from results in previous deliverables.

SECTION 2: EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Oxygen carrier materials.

Two oxygen carriers were tested: one based on iron and the other based on nickel.

2.2. Experimental facility

The high temperature tests were performed in a batch fluidized bed reactor. This reactor was realized and tested for the first time during the GTCLC-NEG Marie Curie Project. The reactor was made of Kanthal, an alloy made of FeCrAl, which allowed to reach high temperatures during the oxidation and reduction steps. The dimensions of the reactor are shown in Figure 1. The final batch plant layout instead it is shown in Figure 2.

REACTOR DIMENSIONS

(*data are in millimeters)

Figure 1: Reactor dimensions (mm).

Figure 2: Layout of the batch fluidized bed reactor system.

Several redox cycles were done at different temperatures: 950°C, 1000°C, 1050°C, 1100°C, 1150°C and 1200°C. In the layout we see that the reacting gases enter from the bottom of the reactor. Reduction was performed for a time of about 2 minutes with CH₄ diluted in N₂ and steam. Water vapor avoids carbon deposition below the distributor plate. The subsequent oxidation was done in air until the oxygen concentration which is typical of air is reached, typically about 10 minutes. Between the reduction and oxidation steps, the gas is switched for 2 minutes to 100% nitrogen, which is used as a purging gas to avoid the mixture of combustible gases with oxygen. The gas velocity is maintained constant at 0.20 m/s in the fluidized bed reactor. The gases flows are regulated by a series of flowmeters.

Gas concentration (CH₄, CO₂, CO, H₂ and O₂) are measured with different systems located at the exit of the reactor.

Inside the reactor about 300 g of oxygen carrier are placed. The pressure drop inside the reactor is monitored with two water columns. At the end of every test, three samples were collected:

- about 25 g from the bed (which is also weighted right after the reactor is opened);
- a sample in the horizontal pipe;
- a sample in the condenser.

To evaluate attrition rate of the oxygen carrier, particles with a particle size below 40 µm were accounted for both in samples in the horizontal pipe and condenser. Particles from samples taken from the bed (~25 g) were characterized to evaluate the evolution of their physic-chemical properties with the high-temperature redox cycles.

SECTION 3: RESULTS

3.1: Tests performed with Fe₂₀γAl:

3.1.1: Oxygen carrier performance during CH₄ combustion tests

The results obtained with iron oxygen carrier (Fe₂₀γAl) are shown in Figure 3. As it can be seen at lower temperatures together with the

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combustion products: carbon dioxide and water vapor also hydrogen and carbon monoxide are produced. These are products of incomplete combustion and their production is mainly due to reforming. With the increase of the temperature both reduction and oxidation reaction happen more rapidly and also more completely and carbon monoxide and hydrogen decrease their concentrations.

Figure 3: Gases analysis at different temperatures with oxygen carrier Fe20γAl

3.1.2: Oxygen carrier characterization

The main physic-chemical properties of the oxygen carrier particles reacted at different temperatures were compared to the analysis performed for the fresh material shown in the deliverable D1.2 on oxygen carrier characterization. The most important results obtained for iron are presented in the following paragraphs.

a) Solids density analysis

Figure 4 shows the evolution of the skeletal density of the solids. The skeletal density slightly increased with the reacting temperature, which suggest that the crystalline structure of the solid may have changed differently depending on the temperature.

Figure 4: Solids density analysis

b) XRD analysis

The crystalline compounds in the solids were identified by XRD analysis; see Figure 5. The main active compound was Fe₂O₃. No iron-aluminates were identified. Therefore, most of iron could be regenerated, and no deactivation of the material could be anticipated. In fact, combustion performance improved with temperature; see Figure 3.

Regarding the alumina, peaks with higher intensity was found for reacted samples. This fact suggest that the crystallinity of the support increased during the reaction, which could be promoted by the Fe-Al interaction during the redox cycles following the reactions:

23AA275P5 (Coupled TwoTheta/Theta)

23AA276P3 (Coupled TwoTheta/Theta)

23AA277P3 (Coupled TwoTheta/Theta)

23AA278P3 (Coupled TwoTheta/Theta)

Figure 5: XRD analysis of Fe₂O₃Al samples reacted at different temperatures. Raw material (1st up), Bed at 950°C (2nd up), Bed at 1000°C (3rd up), Bed at 1050°C (4th up).

c) Reactivity analysis

The reactivity analysis of the samples was performed in an atmospheric TGA with 15 % CH₄ at 950 °C; see Figure 6. In general, reactivity was unchanged after redox cycling at different temperatures. Interestingly, a decrease in the reactivity of the oxygen carrier can be noted in reacted samples reacted at 1050 °C. Additional analysis to the solid samples were carried out to determine the cause of the low reactivity of samples reacted at 1050 °C.

Figure 6: Reactivity analysis of the samples

d) SEM analysis

The appearance of the particles can be observed by SEM analysis; see Figures 7 and 8. The examination of the particles showed that the integrity of the particles could be maintained at the macro-scale in particles reacted at 950 and 1000 °C. Thus, no major cracks could be identified, which suggest that the thermal stress suffered by these particles was low. However, some internal cracks are observed in particles reacted at 1050 °C, which may compromise the mechanical behavior of this material at such high temperature. At the micro-scale, it could be observed that the fresh particles were formed mainly by small porous, which increased in size with the temperature in reacted particles. Then, the solid structure

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showed some sinterization when particles reacted at a higher temperature. This fact could justify the low reactivity of particles reacted at 1050 °C. This behavior could be conditioned by a notorious sinterization of particles in the fluidized bed at this temperature.

Figure 7: solids SEM analysis

Figure 8: Solids SEM analysis, particles cut in section

The internal appearance of the particles also showed some differences depending on the reacting temperature. It can be observed a nucleus-shell structure in fresh particles and particles reacted at 950 and 1000 °C. This pattern disappears in particles reacted at 1050 °C. A SEM-EDX line-scan shows that iron was accumulated in the core of the particles, and some migration to the external surface was observed with the reacting temperature. Eventually, a homogeneous distribution of iron in the particles was achieved at 1050 °C.

Figure 9: SEM-EDX line-scan analysis.

e) Attrition analysis

Fine particles below 40 μm diameter were found in different solid fractions extracted during the tests of the oxygen carrier in the fluidized bed. Figure 10 shows that some fines were elutriated and recovered downstream the reactor. However, most of fine particles remained in the fluidized bed. This fact was confirmed by the particle size distribution analysis of solids in the bed; see Figure 11. Although the mean particle size barely changed (235 μm for fresh vs. 233 μm for reacted particles), it can be seen an appreciable generation of particles below 100 μm in reacted particles. Taking in consideration these results together the appearance of particles in SEM analysis, it can be deduced that particles suffered of some abrasion, but breakage of particles is not detectable.

Figure 10: Attrition analysis

Figure 11: Solids particles diameter of fresh particles and particles reacted at 1050 °C.

f) Mechanical strength

The crushing strength values of the reacted particles at different temperatures are shown in Figure 12. These results are in agreement with the evaluation of the particles done above by other characterization techniques. Thus, the crushing strength barely changed in particles reacted at 950 and 1000 °C; but it showed a relevant decrease for the particles reacted at 1050 °C. The crushing strength of particles reacted at 1050 °C was about 0,5 N, which is below the threshold limit of 1 N usually considered for a proper operation of oxygen carrier particles in a fluidized bed reactor.

Figure 12: Crushing strength of the particles

3.2: Test performed with Ni18 α Al

In a second experimental campaign, it was chosen to use Nickel as oxygen carrier. For this reason it was tested the Ni18 α Al material.

3.2.1: Oxygen carrier performance during CH₄ combustion tests

With the Ni18Al material, we observed a high fraction of hydrogen in the product gases –see Figure 13-, which was due to the high catalytic effect of nickel on the steam methane reforming.

Figure 13: Redox cycles at 1000°C with Ni18Al oxygen carrier

The uncompleted oxidation of hydrogen can be due to the fact that fresh particles calcined at high temperature caused the generation of a form of nickel-aluminate. This form is less reactive than nickel oxide. Also during the reduction step it takes more time to completely reduce the oxygen carrier and the two minutes set previously did not perform effectively following the reaction:

For this reason, as a first solution it was thought to perform reduction with hydrogen for a longer period:

The reduction of nickel aluminate decreased the presence of this compound after its oxidation, and the problem disappeared momentarily at high temperatures because they were sufficient to completely reduce the nickel and avoid the formation of a high fraction of nickel aluminate during the oxidation. However, this effect could not be maintained during the consecutive redox cycles, and eventually high fraction of hydrogen

was again observed. This phenomenon has been studied also in previous works performed at ICB-CSIC. We refer in particular to the thesis of Cristina Dueso¹, which is based on the kinetics of the reaction between nickel oxide and various hydrocarbons (like methane). Thus, nickel was oxidized mainly to NiO by the following reaction:

However, a fraction of nickel could be converted into nickel aluminate in the presence of alumina by:

Thus, NiAl₂O₄ could be accumulated in the particles during consecutive redox cycles, which was promoted by as the reacting temperature increased. A complete overview of the product gas profiles during redox cycles at different temperatures are shown in Figures 14-19. In addition it was observed an improvement of the combustion with the temperature, which may be related to an increase of the reactivity of nickel aluminate with temperature.

Figure 14: Redox reactions at 950°C

¹ Dueso, C. (2010). Combustión de gases con separación inherente de CO₂ mediante transportadores de oxígeno basados en NiO.

Figure 15: Redox reactions at 1000°C

Figure 16: Redox reactions at temperature of 1050°C

Figure 17: Redox reactions at temperature of 1100°C

Figure 18: Redox reactions at temperature of 1150°C

Figure 19: Redox reactions at temperature of 1200°C

The existence of nickel bonded to alumina was proved using TGA analysis. Thus, the low reactive nickel aluminate fraction increased with the reaction temperature in the fluidized bed reactor. But a higher temperature also improved the reactivity of nickel aluminate. This fact suggest that this material could achieve a suitable high reactivity for PCLC process even though nickel aluminate was formed.

3.2.2. Attrition behavior of Ni18Al

Attrition measures of the Ni18Al oxygen carrier are presented in Figure 20. Similar to what was found for the Fe20Al material, fine particles below 40 μm diameter were found in different solid fractions extracted during the tests of the oxygen carrier in the fluidized bed. Some fines were elutriated and recovered downstream the reactor. However, most of fine particles remained in the fluidized bed. The fraction of fine particles showed a relevant increase when the reacting temperature increased from 950 °C to 1100 °C. Then, this increase was of low relevance when temperature was increased up to 1200 °C.

The analysis of the fines produced indicates that this material showed an improved performance compared to the Fe20Al material. Thus, fines produced at 1200 °C with Ni18Al are comparable to fines produced with

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the Fe20Al material at the lowest temperature tested, i.e. 950 °C. This fact makes that the Ni18Al material could be considered as a promising oxygen carrier to be used in the PCLC process.

Figure 20: Nickel attrition measures